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**“GLOBAL RAQAMLI INTEGRATSIYALASHUV:
2030-YILGACHA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHDA
TEXNOLOGIK VA INDUSTRIAL SANOATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH
ORQALI MIKRO VA MAKROIQTISODIY BARQAROR
O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH DOLZARBLIGI”**

**“GLOBAL DIGITAL INTEGRATION: THE RELEVANCE OF
ENSURING MICRO AND MACROECONOMIC SUSTAINABLE
GROWTH THROUGH TECHNOLOGICAL AND INDUSTRIAL
DEVELOPMENT IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN
ECONOMY BY 2030”**

**«ГЛОБАЛЬНАЯ ЦИФРОВАЯ ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ:
АКТУАЛЬНОСТЬ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО
МИКРО- И МАКРОЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА ЧЕРЕЗ
РАЗВИТИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ И ИНДУСТРИАЛЬНОЙ
ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ В ПЕРЕХОДЕ К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ
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- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
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- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
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- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

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ISSUES OF IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF MANAGEMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES

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Abstract. This article examines the theoretical and practical aspects of improving the methodology for managing small industrial zones. The role of small industrial zones in developing the regional economy, attracting investment, creating new jobs, and supporting entrepreneurial activity is analyzed. The article also considers key issues related to the management of industrial zones, factors affecting their efficiency, and the introduction of modern management mechanisms. As a result of the study, scientific and practical proposals and recommendations were developed to improve the effectiveness of small industrial zone management.

Keywords: small industrial zones, management methodology, industrial infrastructure, investment activity, entrepreneurship, economic development, regional economy, digital governance, innovation, efficiency, monitoring, cluster approach, investment attractiveness, industrial policy, economic modernization.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada kichik sanoat zonalarini boshqarish metodologiyasini takomillashtirishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari yoritilgan. Kichik sanoat zonalarining hududiy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish, investitsiyalarni jalb etish, yangi ish o'rinlarini yaratish hamda tadbirkorlik faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlashdagi ahamiyati tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, sanoat zonalarini boshqarishda uchraydigan muammolar, ularning samaradorligiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar hamda zamonaviy boshqaruv mexanizmlarini joriy etish masalalari ko'rib chiqilgan. Tadqiqot natijasida kichik sanoat zonalarini boshqarish samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan ilmiy-amaliy taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kichik sanoat zonalarini boshqaruv metodologiyasi, sanoat infratuzilmasi, investitsion faollik, tadbirkorlik, iqtisodiy rivojlanish, hududiy iqtisodiyot, raqamli boshqaruv, innovatsiyalar, samaradorlik, monitoring, klaster yondashuvi, investitsion jozibadorlik, sanoat siyosati, iqtisodiy modernizatsiya.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются теоретические и практические аспекты совершенствования методологии управления малыми промышленными зонами. Проанализирована роль малых промышленных зон в развитии региональной экономики, привлечении инвестиций, создании новых рабочих мест и поддержке предпринимательской деятельности. Также рассмотрены проблемы, возникающие в процессе управления промышленными зонами, факторы, влияющие на их эффективность, а также вопросы внедрения современных механизмов управления. По результатам исследования разработаны научно-практические предложения и рекомендации, направленные на повышение эффективности управления малыми промышленными зонами.

Ключевые слова: малые промышленные зоны, методология управления, промышленная инфраструктура, инвестиционная активность, предпринимательство, экономическое развитие, региональная экономика, цифровое управление, инновации, эффективность, мониторинг, кластерный подход, инвестиционная привлекательность, промышленная политика, экономическая модернизация.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of the modernization of the national economy and the integrated development of regions, small industrial zones are gaining particular importance as one of the key factors of economic growth. Small industrial zones expand opportunities for locating production capacities, developing small businesses and

private entrepreneurship, ensuring employment, and making effective use of local raw materials. At the same time, they play an important role in attracting investment to the regions, introducing new technologies, and increasing industrial output.

Today, the intensification of globalization processes, the need to enhance the competitiveness of the economy, and the growing demand for innovative development require the effective organization of small industrial zones. In this process, improving the management system, applying modern management methods, introducing digital technologies, and ensuring the rational use of resources are among the most urgent tasks. This is because the efficiency of small industrial zones largely depends on the effectiveness and practical applicability of their management mechanisms.

In this regard, it is important to study the issues of improving the methodology for managing small industrial zones, identifying existing challenges, and developing scientific and practical proposals for addressing them. The economic efficiency of small industrial zones can be further increased by introducing modern management approaches, developing monitoring and evaluation systems, enhancing investment attractiveness, and supporting the activities of resident enterprises.

The relevance of this topic is determined by the growing role of small industrial zones in the national economy, as well as the need to improve the theoretical and practical aspects of managing their activities. The main purpose of the study is to examine the theoretical foundations of the methodology for managing small industrial zones, analyze existing challenges, and develop practical recommendations for their improvement.

Small industrial zones (SIZs) are among the key instruments for diversifying the national economy, promoting industrial development in the regions, creating new jobs, and supporting entrepreneurial activity. Their effective functioning largely depends on the quality and efficiency of the management system. Therefore, improving the methodology for managing the activities of small industrial zones remains one of the most relevant issues today.

The management methodology of small industrial zones should primarily focus on the rational use of available resources, attraction of investments, and effective coordination of resident enterprises. In practice, the insufficient development of infrastructure, the use of outdated management mechanisms, and the incomplete implementation of modern monitoring and control systems in some industrial zones negatively affect their overall performance and development potential.

One of the most important directions for improving management methodology is the widespread adoption of digital management technologies. The use of electronic management systems for monitoring the activities of resident enterprises, supervising the implementation of investment projects, and maintaining integrated databases significantly enhances management efficiency. Such measures contribute to greater speed, transparency, and accuracy in decision-making processes.

In addition, it is necessary to strengthen the strategic planning system within small industrial zones. Developing long-term development strategies based on the economic potential, natural resources, labor market conditions, and logistical advantages of each region can substantially improve the sustainability and effectiveness of industrial zones. In this regard, the application of cluster-based approaches and innovation-driven development principles is of particular importance.

Expanding cooperation between the public and private sectors is another important aspect of improving management methodology. The provision of infrastructure and a favorable legal environment by the state, combined with investment and innovation initiatives undertaken by the private sector, can significantly enhance the competitiveness of industrial zones. Furthermore, the development of consulting, marketing, financial, and logistics support services for resident enterprises will contribute to the more efficient organization and operation of their activities.

Another essential component of improving the management methodology of small industrial zones is the development of a comprehensive performance evaluation system. In this context, it is advisable to use indicators such as production volume, export performance, the number of jobs created, the volume of attracted investments, and tax revenues. Regular assessment based on these indicators will make it possible to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the management system and develop appropriate measures for its continuous improvement.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, small industrial zones play an important role in ensuring the sustainable development of the national economy, expanding industrial production, effectively utilizing the economic potential of regions, and creating new jobs. The effective organization and management of their activities contribute not only to the development of industrial sectors but also to supporting business entities, attracting investment, and increasing export potential.

The study analyzed existing challenges in managing small industrial zones, including issues related to infrastructure provision, the insufficient improvement of management mechanisms, difficulties in coordinating investment processes, and the need to enhance the effectiveness of monitoring systems. Addressing these challenges is an important condition for increasing the economic efficiency of small industrial zones.

The study also substantiated the need for the widespread introduction of digital management technologies, the development of a strategic planning system, the improvement of monitoring and evaluation mechanisms based on performance indicators, the strengthening of public-private partnerships, and the application of innovative management methods as key areas for improving management methodology. These measures will contribute to the efficient use of resources, improve the quality of managerial decision-making, and create more favorable conditions for the activities of resident enterprises.

In addition, the development of cooperative relations among enterprises operating in small industrial zones, the formation of production clusters, and the practical implementation of scientific and technological achievements are important factors in increasing their competitiveness. Industrial zones established on the basis of modern management principles can become growth points of the regional economy and make a significant contribution to strengthening the industrial potential of the country.

Thus, improving the methodology for managing small industrial zones is one of the important strategic directions of economic development. Its effective implementation is of great importance for increasing investment activity, expanding production volumes, ensuring employment, and achieving the long-term economic development of the country.

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